

UNMASKING DEEPFAKE FACE SWAPS USING MULTI-RESOLUTION HYBRID DCT-DWT APPROACH

BHAVANI RANBIDA¹, DEBABALA SWAIN¹, RISHI RAJ²

¹Department of Computer Science, Rama Devi Women's University, Odisha, India

²Department of Computer Science, Liverpool John Moores University, England, UK

E-mail: ¹bhavaniranbida1995@gmail.com, ¹debabala@rdwu.ac.in, ²rishiraj.rr2016@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In today's digital world, the advanced tools for image editing using AI technologies have made it harder to identify whether an image is real or fake. Deepfake face swaps are the most convincing forms of image forgery among different manipulation formats. This study presents a new hybrid method that combines the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) to detect such deepfakes. By breaking the image into different frequency and spatial layers, the proposed method can easily detect the visual inconsistencies happened due to the manipulations. By combining both DCT and DWT, the manipulated regions can be efficiently located. The experiment shows that the proposed hybrid model improves both accuracy and computational performance. It offers a robust and reliable framework for digital image authenticity against the growing deepfake technologies.

Keywords: DCT, DWT, Digital Image Forensic, Deepfake, Multi-Resolution, Counterfeit Detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of deceitful images in deepfake face swaps present a serious risk, including financial gain, disseminating false information, and altering legal evidence etc. Recognizing these manipulated photographs becomes very crucial in journalism, digital media forensics, and crime investigation [1]–[7]. Although several methods have been adopted, but the effectiveness and accuracy for identifying counterfeits remain doubtful. DWT and DCT are the two fundamental techniques used in this study to check authentication of the photos. This proposed work presents a unique multi-resolution approach for counterfeit detection by combining the DCT and DWT. The images are first compressed with DCT and then segmented into many sub-bands using DWT. This enhances counterfeit region identification effectiveness. The suggested strategy has been evaluated through wide testing, which shows that it outperforms the most advanced existing methods for detecting counterfeit images. The proposed technique is also helpful in photo authentication applications and accurate tamper detection.

The remaining paper is structured as follows. The Section 2 narrates different techniques for deepfake image detection. The Section 3 gives a complete discussion on the existing literature in the related area. Section 4 discusses the proposed research,

while Section 5 presents the experimental outputs and their interpretations. The paper is concluded in section 6 along with the potential avenues as future work.

2. DEEPFAKE IMAGE COUNTERFEIT DETECTION

The practice of utilizing advanced deep learning algorithms to detect and stop image alteration is known as Deepfake Image forgery detection. Latest artificial intelligence algorithms are used in "deepfakes," to produce visually appealing but entirely manipulated images and videos. Deepfake technology, which is particularly concerning when it comes to image forge since it may be used to build a complete change in the original image, add non-existent persons, or seamlessly alter looks. For the purpose of the detecting deepfake digital photo forgeries, sophisticated algorithms or methods and AI models which are trained to find out patterns and abnormalities indicating of manipulation are tend to be used. These methods might be included to analyse the overall cohesiveness of the image, analysing the features of the person's face, and analysing contrasts in the lighting and shadows.

Figure 1 shows a deepfake face swap scenario with Lena and Deepika Padukone's photos where (a) represents the original version of Lena image and (b) represents the deepfake version of Lena image with

Deepika Padukone's face. In such cases it is very difficult to identify the original image with open eyes.

Figure 1: Deepfake forgery (a) Original (b) Deepfake face swapped with Deepika Padukone's face

The capacity to figure out between real and manipulated images is the main objective of deepfake image forgery identification. This is essential for reduce the possible harm brought about by the spread of false information, dishonest business practices, or the malicious use of fake material in a variety of industries, such as; journalism, entertainment, and security. Getting very close of possible risks posed by misleading image modification requires continual study and the development of strong detection algorithms, especially given the rapid expansion of deepfake technology.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

Although there are several studies on digital image forgery detection using spatial-domain and frequency-domain techniques. Most existing methods focus on either handcrafted features with limited robustness or deep learning models. But the problem is, it requires large-scale datasets and high computational resources. Many DWT and DCT-based approaches have shown incredible accuracy. However, their performance often degrades under post-processing operations such as compression, resizing, and noise addition, which are common in real-world scenarios. Furthermore, limited attention has been paid to evaluating the effectiveness of these methods against emerging AI-based forgeries such as deepfakes and face-swap images. The lack of a unified framework that balances detection accuracy, computational efficiency, and robustness against advanced manipulations represents a significant research gap. These unresolved issues clearly establish the need for the present work, which aims to develop and critically evaluate a DWT-DCT-based approach capable of addressing these limitations.

In 2022, Wolter, M., et al. [1] presented a novel approach for detecting deepfake image forgery that

utilizes a coupling of wavelets and CNN with DCT approach for feature extraction. It uses a combination of wavelets and CNN with DCT technique for feature extraction. It reaches a high accuracy rate of 96.75%.

In 2021, Agarwal, A et al. [2] proposed an approach, the MD-CSDNetworkn technique, which combines spatial and frequency domain information for increased face forgery detection. The technique, which takes inspiration from multitask learning, learns an ideal shared representation using features in both the spectral and spatial domains by use of a cross-stitched network architecture. This approach gives accuracy for high-quality images: 97.28% and for low-quality images: 87.57%.

Figure 2: Framework of the Technique [2]

In 2021, Qureshi, A. et al. [3] present a different deepfake video detection method. That method combines blockchain technology with hybrid watermarking method. It creates fictitious films using the Wav2Lip algorithm, emphasising lip-synching precision. The Spanish Government and the EIG CONCERT-Japan call provided money for the research.

Figure 3: Framework of the Technique [3]

In 2022, Solaiyappan, S et al. [4] carried out a thorough analysis of the effectiveness of several deep learning and machine learning models in addition to approaches for separating pictures in order to identify manipulation using GAN-based techniques. The study exhibits exceptional ability in confidently identifying intentionally created abnormalities in medical imaging with 97% accuracy.

In 2022, M. Nawaz et al. [5] have given a novel ResNet-Swish-Dense54 model for detecting

deepfakes in visual data. This method was broadly tested on DFDC, FaceForensic++, and Celeb-DF datasets, demonstrating its effectiveness and generalization ability. The model also showed resilience against various adversarial attacks. Notably, their approach achieved accuracies of 81.51% on DFDC, 70.04% on CelebDF, and 98.60% on FF++.

In 2021, Yuankun Yang et al. [6] presented FaceGuard, a proactive deepfake detection tool, in 2021. It embeds watermarks into actual face photos using a deep learning-based watermarking approach. It compares the retrieved watermark with the actual image to detect spoof faces. It gives accuracy rates: 99.2% on FaceForensics++, 93.9% on DFDC, and 97.6% on Trump-Cage datasets.

In 2022, Jie Liu et al. [7] introduced a novel approach for face forgery detection using Multi-Scale Wavelet Transformer. It provides the multi-scale analysis of Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and the scientists-derived multi-level frequency representations. The ACC ranged from 86.6% to 98.6% for different datasets e.g. DF c40, F2F c40, FS c40, NT c40, FF++ c23, and FF++ c40.

In 2021, Gengyun Jia et al. [8] proposed a face forgery detection method that combines stationary wavelet decomposition, dual-branch network and bilinear feature fusion. By addressing intra and inter image inconsistencies through feature enhancement and extraction, the model effectively extracts the features. It showed superiority in terms of accuracies reaching 80.8% and 75.6% on FF++ datasets. It has got a near-perfect accuracies of 99.9% on UADFV and 99.6% on Celeb-DF datasets.

In 2021, Run Wang et al. [9] introduced a novel approach for contending the distribution of DeepFakes called FakeTagger. By embedding messages into images for Deepfake provenance, FakeTagger represents an efficient way for privacy preservation. Experimental results show the efficiency of FakeTagger, with an average accuracy exceeding 88.95% across various DeepFake types.

In 2022, Paarth Neekhara et al. [10] proposed a semi-fragile watermark technique based on deep learning called FaceSigns. It ensures the integrity of digital images and detects facial forgery. This study produces imperceptible watermarks while maintaining semi-fragile characteristics. It achieves an incredible ACC of 99.6% with FaceSigns. Also surpassing benchmarks like StegaStamp, HiDDeN and SemiFragile DCT.

In 2024, V. Convertini et al. [14] proposed a deepfake detection method using DFT based on analysing image frequency components. This study explores the properties of images to identify the forged areas due to GAN-based generative models. Especially, StyleGAN and StyleGAN2. This study has compared the forged face images generated by the GANs with real images from standard datasets, like FFHQ and CelebA-HQ. It has used machine learning classifiers like SVM and Random Forests for classification. Also discussed about the limitations in generalizing different GAN architectures.

Table 1: A comparison of deepfake forgery detection methods

Sl. No	Author	Method Used	Type of Image	ACC	Advantages / Disadvantages
1	Wolter, M., et al. [1]	Wavelets, CNN with DCT	Deepfake	96.75%	High accuracy rate - Utilizes wavelets and CNN with DCT for feature extraction Disadvantage: Concerns about potential abuse due to publicly available detection code
2	Agarwal, A et al. [2]	Cross-stitched network architecture	Face forgery	97.28%	Combines spatial and frequency domain information - Effective in intra-database and cross-database evaluations
3	Qureshi, A et al. [3]	Hybrid watermarking, blockchain, Wav2Lip algorithm	Deepfake video	Not provided	Combines watermarking and blockchain technology - Focuses on lip-syncing accuracy Disadvantage: Not evaluated

					for other types of deepfake attacks
4	Solaiyappan, S et al. [4]	Machine learning, deep learning, GAN-based methods	Medical imaging	97 %	High accuracy rate - Effective detection of artificially generated anomalies in medical imaging
5	M. Nawaz et al. [5]	Deep learning	Visual data (DFDC, FaceForensic++, Celeb-DF datasets)	81.51% - 98.60%	Effective on various visual deepfakes - Resilient against adversarial attacks Disadvantage: Requires further evaluation against crafted attacks
6	Yuankun Yang et al. [6]	Deep-learning-based watermarking, JPEG compression	Deepfake face images	99.2% - 99.5%	- Proactive approach to deepfake detection - High accuracy rates for adaptive deepfakes
7	Jie Liu et al. [7]	Multi-scale Wavelet Transformer	Face forgery	86.6% - 98.6%	- Utilizes Discrete Wavelet Transform for multi-level frequency representations - Effective feature fusion
8	Gengyun Jia et al. [8]	Stationary wavelet decomposition, dual-branch network, bilinear feature fusion	Face forgery	80.8% - 99.9%	- Dual-branch network effectively extracts intra-image and inter-image inconsistencies -

					Achieves high accuracy rates
9	Run Wang et al. [9]	Watermarking for Deepfake provenance	Deepfake	>88.95 %	- Proactively defends against DeepFakes - Offers robustness, effectiveness, and stealthiness
10	Paarth Neekharra et al. [10]	Semi-fragile neural watermarks	Media authentication	99.60%	- Produces imperceptible watermarks while maintaining semi-fragile characteristics - Reliable detection of Deepfake facial manipulations
11	Convertini et al. [14]	Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT)	deepfake image	99 %	Analysing image frequency components to identify artifacts by GAN-based generative models,

The key contribution of this study is a hybrid frequency-domain recognition approach that integrates Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) with Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). It features and applies them to multi-resolution face-swap deepfakes digital images for forgery localization. Prior works use DWT or DCT individually for classification, target generic copy-move/splicing attacks, or perform whole-image deepfake classification. Our proposed method explicitly fuses DWT high-frequency maps and DCT coefficient statistics to detect, localise, and robustly handle compression and scale changes in modern face-swap deepfakes.

4. PROPOSED WORK

In the proposed research work, two popular transformation techniques are used, i.e., DCT and DWT. DCT is used first to lower its dimensionality,

then it produces blocking artefacts, which help in the detection of fraud [12]. in the next step, we use DWT in the DCT compressed image. It splits the image into four sub-bands, i.e., LL, LH, HL, and HH sub-bands [13]. We represent the deepfake image of Lena in Figure 4 (c), which is a face-swapping image of Lena and Deepika Padukone in represented in Figures 4 (a and b).

Figure 4: (A) Lena image (B) Deepika Padukone image (C) Deepfake face swapped image

4.1. Pre-processing

4.1.1. Transformation of Color image to Grayscale image

In the first step of pre-processing the input colour image (Im) of dimension M × N pixels were converted to a grayscale image (Im_gray). This can be accomplished by utilising the following formula:

$$Im_gray = 0.229R + 0.587G + 0.114B \quad (1)$$

The grayscale conversion of the input image (Im) is achieved by computing the weighted sum of the RGB color components of each pixel in the image [1]. The resulting grayscale image (Im_gray) has the same dimensions, as per the input image and represents the luminance (brightness) values of each pixel. The use of grayscale conversion in image processing and computer vision applications is common practice as it simplifies the image data and reduces computational complexity.

Figure 5: Workflow of the Proposed Approach

4.1.2. Resizing the Grayscale image

Reducing the size of image to 1024×1024 if the image dimensions are greater than 1024 pixels. This step is to reduce the processing time and make it more reliable.

4.2. Apply Discrete Wavelet Transform

The proposed approach utilizes DWT with the Haar wavelet for multi-level decomposition of images. This enables dimensionality reduction and extraction of meaningful features from sub-bands, enhancing subsequent image analysis and manipulation.

DWT involves sequential filtering of a signal using a low-pass filter:

$$y[n] = (x * g)[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k]g[n - k] \quad (2)$$

The signal is further decomposed concurrently by employing a high-pass filter h . As a result, two sets of coefficients are obtained. The high-pass filter gives rise to the detail coefficients and the low-pass filter obtains the approximation coefficients. It is crucial to note that these two filters are intricately connected and referred to as quadrature mirror filters as mentioned below:

Figure 6: Approximation coefficients and detail coefficients decomposed with high and low pass filters

DWT involves sub-sampling and applying additional filtering with lower cutoff frequencies.

$$y_{low}[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k]g[2n - k] \quad (3)$$

$$y_{high}[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k]h[2n - k] \quad (4)$$

Although DWT reduces the time resolution of the image but it improves frequency resolution through altered filtering.

Figure 7: Extraction of LL, LH, HL and HH coefficients [1]

In Figure 12, 2↓1: shows the decimation operation, where the even indexed samples is only considered, L: represents Low Sub-Band Image, H represents High Sub-Band Image and I represent Fused Image.

4.3. Apply Discrete Cosine Transform

The proposed method utilises DCT for image compression and forgery detection. It transforms the image to the frequency domain by reducing data size while preserving important features. It efficiently detects tampered regions by analysing frequency components by ensuring accurate image analysis.

$$f(x, y) = \frac{2}{N} c(u)c(v) \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N f(x, y) \cos \left[\frac{(2x+1)u\pi}{2N} \right] \cos \left[\frac{(2y+1)v\pi}{2N} \right] \quad (5)$$

Below is the DCT equation represented as F(u,v)

$$F(u, v) = \frac{2}{N} c(u)c(v) \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N F(u, v) \cos \left[\frac{(2x+1)u\pi}{2N} \right] \cos \left[\frac{(2y+1)v\pi}{2N} \right] \quad (6)$$

Once the compression is applied, the images are reconstructed from their transform by employing the Inverse-DCT equation, f(x,y) [15].

4.4. Post-Processing

4.4.1. Initialisation of Threshold

It is a crucial step in image analysis to detect the spliced areas. The threshold value is established to identify the potential tampered regions based on block analysis. Accurate threshold of an image ensures image integrity without tampering.

4.4.2. Applying Binary Masking

After correlation, the resulting image is converted into a binary form. Here a black pixel represents a forged pixel and a white pixel represent the un-forged pixel. In this way, it enables easy detection and visualization of the tampered and un-tampered regions.

4.4.3. Noise Reduction

The proposed approach refines the edges of the detected regions and removes smaller objects with lesser number of pixels from the binary image using Gaussian noise reduction method. By doing so, the unwanted noise can be easily reduced. Also, the forged region is accurately marked white color.

4.4.4. Forged Region Detection and Localization

Morphological operations are used to modify the shape or structure of an image. They are particularly useful for refining the edges of the detected regions and enhancing the visual appearance of the image. By using morphological operations, it can be ensure that the tampered regions are accurately identified.

4.4.5. Performance Measurement Parameters

The accuracy of the proposed technique can be measured as follows,

Accuracy (ACC): It represents the accurate percentage of the authentic pixels found in the test images.

$$ACC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FN+F} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

True Positive (TP) = The number of forged samples that are correctly identified as forged by the classifier.

True Negative (TN) = The number of authentic images that are correctly recognised as authentic by the classifier.

False Positive (FP) = The number of authentic images that are incorrectly labeled as forged by the classifier

False Negative (FN) = The number of forged images that are incorrectly classified as authentic by the classifier[9].

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

$$TNR = \frac{TN}{TN+F} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

$$FPR = (1 - TNR) \times 100\% \quad (10)$$

5. SIMULATION AND RESULT ANALYSIS

The experiments were conducted on various resolutions of standard deepfake images using a Python programming platform running on an Intel Core i3-1125G4 @ 2.00GHz processor. In Figure 8; the cover image depicts Lena's face replaced with that of Deepika Padukone, making it challenging to distinguish the forged deepfake with open eyes. We identified altered regions in six different resolutions of the deepfake images listed in Table 2. Our proposed methodology for detecting forged areas was validated using several test parameters, including PSNR, SSIM, NC and execution time.

In Figure 9, experiments for detecting deepfake altered areas were conducted on color images of Baboon and Lena.

Figure 8: Deepfake images and corresponding forged Area localized in Multiple Resolutions

Table 2: PSNRs, SSIMs, NCs and Processing Time of Detected Deepfake Images with Multi-Resolution

Image Size	PSNR	SSIM	NC	Processing Time (in Sec)
2048 × 2048	54.27	0.99	0.004	0.219
1843 × 1843	50.03	0.99	0.013	0.172
1638 × 1638	46.35	0.99	0.149	0.14
1434 × 1434	45.39	0.99	-0.001	0.109
1229 × 1229	47.66	0.99	0.05	0.125
1024 × 1024	48.65	0.99	0.05	0.047

Figure 9: Forged Area Detection in Baboon and Lena Image (A) Original Image, (B) Deepfake Image, (C) Grayscale Deepfake Image and (D) Detected Forged Area

The proposed approach has tested with multiple wavelet methods such as bior, coif, db, dmey, haar, rbio and sym [19]. Figure 10 is representing the NCs and Processing Time for each wavelet methods tested with the approach.

Figure 10: Representation of Deepfake images and corresponding Detected Tampered Area with Multi-Resolution and their corresponding NCs and Processing Time (in sec) using various Wavelets

The findings of this study demonstrate that the combination of DWT and DCT features yields detection performance in different AI-generated deepfakes and face swaps in multi-resolution, achieving robustness against compression and geometric attacks like rotation and scaling. The performance of the proposed approach has been evaluated with 230 deepfake forged images. The proposed model reached 98.11% accuracy, 98.07% TPR, and 0.02% FPR, as listed in Table 3. Both DWT and DCT are capable of capturing manipulation artifacts with lower computational complexity while maintaining competitive performance. The ROC curves for the test images are displayed in Figure 11. Figure 12 presents an image of the proposed technique's accuracy on different geometric transformations, which is tested on 230 images that have undergone different geometric transformations. Recent studies published in 2024 predominantly rely on deep learning and hybrid CNN-Transformer architectures, which report high detection accuracy but often require large datasets and significant computational resources. The findings of this work emphasize the continued relevance of transform-domain techniques, particularly for lightweight, interpretable, and resource-efficient forensic applications.

Figure 11: ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) Curves on a set of images

Table 3: Performance Comparison of the Proposed Technique on Deepfake Forgery Detection

Approaches	ACC	TPR	FPR
Proposed	98.11	98.07	0.02
[1]	96.75	97	3.5
[2]	97.28	93.5	4.02
[4]	97	98.8	3.08
[5]	90.05	93	4.05

Figure 12: Accuracy of the Proposed Technique against different Geometric Transformations

6. CONCLUSION

This study represents a novel and efficient approach for detecting deepfake face swap manipulations in digital images using a multi-resolution hybrid model. It combines the strengths of DCT and DWT. The proposed method is very accurate in finding the forged areas because it can detect small errors and unusual patterns that appeared in the manipulated image. Compared to conventional techniques, our hybrid DCT-DWT framework achieves superior detection performance with a lower FPR that help the image forgery detection more reliable.

However, a critical assessment reveals certain shortcomings. The detection performance may degrade when images with high compression or unseen manipulation techniques are generated by advanced AI models. This research adds value to digital image forensics by dealing with the current gaps in earlier detection approaches and providing a practical, computationally efficient solution to counter the growing threat of deepfake face swaps. Looking ahead, the method can be further improved through the integration of deep learning-based feature extraction, adaptive thresholding, and multi-modal fusion techniques to reduce false negatives and strengthen robustness against emerging deepfake technologies. The analysis of existing deepfake detection techniques shows that frequency-

based features can be successfully utilised to distinguish between original and manipulated images, particularly in high-frequency components [14]. Further studies in this domain will help protect the genuineness and integrity of digital visuals as AI-based editing becomes more widespread. The proposed work represents a meaningful and timely contribution to the field of digital image forensics. Particularly addressing AI-generated image manipulations such as deepfakes and face swaps. At last it can be summarized that the proposed framework represents a strong foundational step towards developing lightweight, interpretable, and computationally efficient forensic systems. However, continued research is necessary to meet the real-world deployment challenges.

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